

THE IMPACT OF MOTIVATION MILLENNIAL GENERATION TO JOB PERFORMANCE IN E- COMMERCE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The increase of e-commerce in Indonesia has attracted the millennials rather than non-ecommerce company. E-Commerce business in Indonesia, especially in Jakarta and it will increase rivalry among the businesses that will affect the motivation of the employees. Also the scope of the millennial age will put a limitation on this research. This study will also analyze the difference of working behavior between millennial generation and the previous generation. With a lot of E-Commerce businesses established recently, will it be motivate the employees or the other way around. Most of millennial prefer to work in e-commerce industry than in any other industries because of their lifestyle is tech-savvy which they always using gadgets and any other online platform as their main source of information. The Result shows that each independent variable that are individual needs, personal preference, working environment, and tech-savvy are supported towards the dependent variable which is job performance. All of those variables are positively related towards job performance.

Keywords: E-commerce; Millenial. Work performance; Tech-savvy.

1. Introduction

Motivation is something that will affect people behavior towards their working performance in a company. Motivated employees will help an organization to achieve bigger target, because they are motivated to keep looking forward to get better work performance (Ali & Ahmed, 2009). Employees with highly motivated towards their work, will perform better in their company to achieve bigger target. However, employees with lower 2 motivation will not perform well towards their works, and will causing a lot of disadvantages to the company. High motivation towards employees will come according to their passion when they are given a task by the organization. Employee motivation always been a major concern by a management apart from the economy is growing or shrinking. To measure employees' motivation, management should create an employee's performance evaluation.

According to Brian Fetherstonhaugh in 2014, there are five reasons that motivate people to work in E-Commerce industry nowadays. The first reason is E-Commerce has a fantastic long-term global growth because it is predicted to grow 17% per year, and E-Commerce is just begins. The second reason because E-Commerce make people think like a general manager since it gives intense skills of business including marketing, supply chain, pricing, and profit management. The third reason is encouraging the 3 employee a deep appreciation towards the value of branding experience and customer experience. The next reason could be E-Commerce give chances to do lot of testing, and immediately will get feedback card from the customer. The last reason will be, E-Commerce is practical and relevant that will last a lifetime.

Employee's performance will be graded in an organization at the end of the month (Regan, 2017). The purpose of employee's performance evaluation is to know whether the employees are working on track or not. Employees will be given a feedback and critic from the employee's performance evaluation, so they could know what their strength is and what is they're lack of when performing their job in a month. Employee's performance evaluation will give the employees knowledge about what the organization is expect from them. Employees with a good performance usually will get a special reward to keep them highly motivated towards their job. When giving employee's performance evaluation, a good communication is needed in order to make the process of evaluation is effective and know exactly the needs and major concerns of the workforce.

Generation Y or millennial think that work is one of the most important things in order to building career (Howee and Strauss, 2012) and it is very important to create a condition that will increase the commitment of the employees within an organization in a long term. What is meant by condition is fun, to motivate. Fun environment will increase the motivation of generation Y employees, then it will bring good impact towards their job performance (Yanti, 2012).

E-commerce also known as electronic commerce may define as process of buying and also selling either products or services through electronic system like Internet or any other computer network (Devandra, 4 2012). The purpose of e-commerce is to help and offer an easier way to a company for their daily business transaction activities. E-commerce firstly founded in the early 1970s. A company to send documents like purchase orders or invoices electronically used it. World Wide Web or known as WWW was later introduced in 1994, which predicted by many known researches that e-commerce type of business will become important type of business in the world of business later on (Nanehkaran, 2013). The first E-Commerce business was introduced in 1998 and was made by USA and some countries in Europe. In 2005, E-Commerce was expanded to Asia and later on become one of the most important in the world of economy until nowadays.

According to Cannarelli in 2017, with the implementation of ECommerce, they just not bring advantages to the business but also for the consumer. Below is the list of advantages of E-Commerce from the seller and buyer perspectives. • E-Commerce could help the seller to increase their market size to go global • Reduce the use of paper in any kind of activities like design, production, packaging, distribution, and also marketing. • Help businesses that selling specific products that they could not market it physically because of limited consumer. • Reduce the time and the cost of promotion since the specification of the item will be shown in the Internet. • Connect businesses within a country. • Increase the creativity of the citizen. • Increase the buying power, since the seller may reduce the price because low cost of production. • Reduce the unemployment rate since it will motivate the citizen to open up a business with lower cost of capital.

The benefits of E-Commerce will suitable with the working style of millennial generation, since they are considered as educated, motivated, tech-savvy, cost effective, aware of the competition, and expressive (Hussein Oz, 2017).

E-Commerce first came to Indonesia was in year 1996, with the established of D-net that known as online transaction website. E-Commerce could be one of the most promising businesses in Indonesia since Indonesia is ranked number 4 as the world most populated country in the world. However, with the lack of buying power and infrastructure of telecommunication by the citizen of Indonesia, the popularity of E-Commerce only known in Indonesian big cities. With that case, most of E-Commerce businesses mainly focusing in the big cities like Jakarta, Bandung, and Bali Island (Mo Morris, 2016).

Table 1. E-Commerce company by ranking 2017

Rank	E-Commerce Company
1	Tokopedia
2	Bukalapak
3	Lazada
4	OLX

The increase of e-commerce in Indonesia has attracted the millennials rather than non-ecommerce company. The researcher wants to identify the factors that the millennial are looking on becoming an employee in ecommerce.

Such as the benefits, the advantages, and factors that driven the millennials. Especially the number of e-commerce in Indonesia is keep on increasing, what factors that differentiate from one e-commerce (Lazada, Bukalapak, Tokopedia) between one and another.

The problem that could be stated in this study could be there are a lot E-Commerce business in Indonesia, especially in Jakarta and it will increase rivalry among the businesses that will affect the motivation of the employees. Also the scope of the millennial age will put a limitation on this research. This study will also analyze the difference of working behavior between millennial generation and the previous generation. With a lot of E-Commerce businesses established recently, will it be motivate the employees or the other way around. Most of millennial prefer to work in e-commerce industry than in any other industries because of their lifestyle is tech-savvy which they always using gadgets and any other online platform as their main source of information (Kane, 2017).

It was mentioned that the age range of millennial is from 23-40 (Schorer, 2017). However, millennial might reflect a different behavior based from age and gender. Also there are a lot of E-Commerce company in the 14 industry that may reflect different tasks and working environment, that makes a reason why millennial generation choose to work on that certain company (Annissa, 2017).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Individual Needs

A need is something that is necessarily possessed by every individual or human being. It is something that the consumer must have to make them feel relaxed or ease. Therefore, individual need becoming a priority and must be fulfilled. Individual needs can be mood changing for some people, and a determining factor to drive people's motivation. In this case, to achieve full potential that can be delivered by the employees in the office, a company should be able to fulfill the employees need, in this term is the salary, and working environment. According to Maslow Theory, need defined as a psychological or psychological feeling that must be satisfied or fulfilled. A need can influence the behaviors, motivation, and work attitudes of a person. According to Maslow theory hierarchy of needs is divided into 5 groups from the most needed to least needed. Those are physiological needs, security and safely needs, social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization. Starting from the physiological needs to be satisfied. To safety needs at work, in this case is a safety from unemployment, loss of income because of sickness, etc. In the Social needs aspect, some people want to be recognized, be a part of a group, a support from friends, family, and relatives, and also from the co- 17 worker and supervisors itself that is cooperative. In the esteem needs, a compliment and given a recognition for the good work that is done and maintained by the employees is necessarily needed, as a form of respecting one and another, and also to increase the self-esteem of an employee to do their job better. As for the self-actualization is about how the employee reflect themselves and measure their extent of success and able to complete the tasks regarding the challenges aligned at work (Ramlall, 2004). And for the external is giving an incentive for the employees as a token of appreciation for their hard work and dedication throughout years working for the company, and increase the company's performance (Ramlall, 2004)

2.2 Personal Preferences

The employee should able to complete all the tasks and assignments given. According to Peters & Zelewski (2007), the assignments given may affect the employee's motivation, because the employees are more motivated to complete the assignments that is related to their interest and ability. Therefore, the employees are having their own preferences when it comes to something that might affect their work performance, such as reasonable salary, conducive working environment, and provided training or job development by the company (Lange & Houran, 2010). It is needed by almost every employee to get what they want. Although the employees do not always can get a raise on salary, etc. the company can substitute it through giving incentive or reward system.

A reward system is one of the factors and preferences of the employee to gain more productivity and motivation on doing their work. An employee who are working hard and beneficial for the company need to be appreciated, to motivate and make them loyal to the company (Cohen et al., 2013). Good reward system is one of many other personal preferences that is benefitting and able to motivate the employees. Giving out promotions, increasing the salary, etc. are focused by the companies to motivate their employees which to increase the quality of the employees work performance (Subramani, 2001).

2.3 Work Environment

According to Kohun (1992), working environment is entirely affecting and compromise the actions, and motivations on the employee's activities and performance. The employees can work on their full potential if the environment and surroundings are supporting to them. It can be delivered through the supervisors, and co-workers that are supportive to one and another, can share knowledge and thoughts regarding work related topic, and value and another as a team with one vision and mission which is to improve 20 the company performance (Brenner,

2004). Which benefiting the company to improve the effectiveness of its employees. Moreover, the environment of the office must be designed to allow the employees to be more create and have the courage to share their thoughts, feelings, and opinions to have a good productivity.

According to Opperman (2002) working environment divided into three components or elements which are technical environment, human environment, and the organizational environment. The technical environment aspect categorized as the tools, equipment, and facilities that is provided by the company for their employees. Meanwhile for the human environment aspect refers to how the employees treat one and another, barriers between bosses and the employees, informal interaction in the office to allow the employees to share their thoughts and exchange ideas related to the work and assignments (Stewart, 2010).

2.4 Tech-Savvy on Work Performance

Technology era has showing a significant improvement in the technology growth. One of the phenomenal technology that is given to the society is internet. It has been very helpful to the business through the communication tools, and information gathering. In business sector, internet does a favor on those three things, consumer can reach the company or business through their social media, which categorized as new CRM tools between the company and the customer. Millennials is the generation that has the biggest 22 involvement in the technology era. Therefore, it is called tech-savvy or generation of technology (Heywood & Elsworth, 2007., McNamara, 2006., Prensky, 2001).

Technology is helpful to many companies. It increases the efficiency of the employees and maximize their potential. Employees can have a 24/7 access to resources, and data collection through internet. Every data gathering can be conducted through technology (internet). Therefore, it is become easier to conduct a research, and information gathering regarding the demographic, issue, patterns, and behavior of the society (consumer, employees, etc). The work of an employees is more efficient and flexible due to the technology involvement (Devi & Jyothsna, 2014). Therefore, lot of company are giving a training to its employees every time a new technology that is helpful to the company are introduced. It is conducted to improve the knowledge and understanding of the employees to the new technology (hardware/software), to improve the efficiency of their works

2.5 Job Performance

There are internal and external factors that are involved in the job performance. Employee's intellectual level, capability, and motivation is a determining factor that affect the job performance of an employee. The company should be strict and be more selective on choosing their candidates to be part of organization, candidates that is recruited should be the one that suits the job position well. Second, the company also must improve the human resource and knowledge of its employees, because market and businesses are fluctuating and must keep up with other business to survive in the market. A monthly or yearly training should be conducted to improve the knowledge and performance of the employees to perform better, and maximize their potential (Daft, 1984). The last one is the employee's motivation. Does not matter on how big is the employee's potential and ability to do the work, it will not be maximized and make a good performance if the employee does not have the motivation to do the job (Deal & Kennedy, 1982).

A performance can also be shown from the individuals through their progress, ability to complete the assignments, and able to achieve the target. The factors that involves the job performance of the employees are the willingness to explore and try something new, which will bring the productivity of the employees (Oluseyi & Ayo). This aspect is contributing a lot to the company's success. A good job performance is necessarily needed from the employees 24 by showing a commitment, creativity, discipline, and innovation (Kreisman, 2002). According to Sinha (2001), the employee's willingness and openness is also a determining factor regarding their productivity and performance on doing their job. To improve the performance, the employee need to set a target that need to be achieved and keep the task on track. Therefore, the employee will have a better management regarding their tasks and deadlines, which later affecting the company's performance (Stup, 2003). Meanwhile on the psychological needs, the company and supervisors must be able to support and knowledge sharing regarding the job activities, giving encouragement and credit for a job well done, to increase the morale and motivation of the employees to do better and self-confidence, which to improve the employee performance (Blau,1964).

2.6 Relationship between employee motivation and job performance

Every person has their own motivation as a key point on conducting their activity. It is the main factor that driven the employees to complete their assignments and tasks given, which the interior drive that person to act (Chaudhary & Sharma, 2012). If the company can identify the needs of their employees, will be able to drive the motivation of the employees to do their work better. An employee who are working with full motivation by their needs fulfilled will be able to focus on their works and not thinking about anything else beside the assignments and tasks given (Chaudhary & Sharma, 2012). An employee that are motivated will carrying on his or her best to complete the assignments and tasks, and improved the productivity which later valued by the company.

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From the employee motivation factor describes that when those 3 factors, which are the individual needs, personal preferences, and working environment are fulfilled, the employees' motivation will be significantly increasing, and intend to do their job better and perform well for the company that has treat them well. It is important for the company to value the 26 employees' wants and needs, and those who perform well and benefitting the company (Carlsen, 2003).

2.7 Research Framework

Figure 1. Framework

Hypothesis:

- H1. Individual needs is positively related to Job Performance
- H2. Personal preferences is positively related to Job Performance
- H3. Work environment is positively related to Job Performance
- H4. Tech-savvy is positively related to Job Performance

3. Methodology

In the research design, the researcher will elaborate into three sections which is unit of analysis, sampling method, and number of sample to ease the researcher on finding the correct respondents, and identify the number of respondents need to support this research.

The unit of analysis for this research will be different from the original research, which is focusing on the millennials that is 18 years old and above, working on specifically e-commerce business and having an experience for at least a year. The millennials that work on e-commerce businesses must be work in Tokopedia, Bukalapak, and Lazada. This unit selection must applied to identify the eligibility of the respondents to participate in the unit selection for this research.

The researcher will choose 150 respondents who are at least working on e-commerce business for a year, the respondents also must be millennials, and above 18 years old that work in Jakarta area. The researcher will conduct

a validity and reliability test before distributing the questionnaires to real 30 respondents. The reliability and validity test conducted to guarantee the quality of the questionnaires, and to check whether the questions in the questionnaire are on track to become a supporting data for this research. 30 pre-test questionnaires will be given to the respondents for the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, followed by wording test to identify the grammar and spelling error, also to identify the understanding of the respondents throughout the questionnaire.

Cross sectional technique will be conducted due to the time constraint given. The method will be quantitative method, to identify the positive relationship between individual needs, personal preferences, and working environment towards job performance in the e-commerce business for millennials.

To assess the data and the hypothesis gathered from the data collection, the researcher will conduct the data analysis method. In this research, the researcher will only use 1 regression to measure the independent and dependent variables. 1 multiple linear regression need to be conducted to investigate the positive relationship between the independent variables towards dependent variable. The statistical software used by the researcher to analyze the data is SPSS, which to obtain the result and identify the motivations of the millennials on working on the ECommerce business.

There are 2 ways for the researcher to test the hypothesis. Multiple linear regression and Simple linear regression. The researcher is using only multiple linear regression for this study, because there is no simple linear regression hypothesis to be tested.

The researcher is using only multiple linear regression to analyze multiple independent variables with one dependent variable. The usage of the multiple linear regressions for this research will be shown in the following hypothesis:

H1: Individual needs is positively related to Job Performance

H2: Personal preferences is positively related to Job Performance

H3: Work environment is positively related to Job Performance

With the formula: $Y = a + Bx_1 + Bx_2$

Job Performance = a + B1*Individual Needs + B2*Personal Preferences + B3*Work Environment + B4*Tech-Savvy

Whereas:

A: estimated constant

Bn: regression coefficient of each variable

E: Error

4. Result and Analysis

The researcher has distributed 150 questionnaires to be filled out by the targeted respondents. Before distributed 150 questionnaires, the researcher has conducted pre-test that distributed to 30 respondents in order to check the data validity and reliability of each questions in the questionnaire, which going to be use in the main data collection by using SPSS.

Pre-test were conducted before the researcher distributed the main questionnaire to gather all of the data. The researcher has distributed 30 questionnaires to be filled out by 30 respondents in order to check the reliability and validity of the data for each question. All of the data was calculated with software called SPSS.

4.1 Descriptive statistic

The researcher will be using descriptive research through quantitative method, followed by using survey questions as the method to approach the direct answer from the respondents. The purpose of using descriptive research is to identify the elements of an existing theory and formed to a new theory, which from an employee's motivation on job performance to millennials motivation towards job performance. There are two techniques that can be used in descriptive research, which are cross sectional and longitudinal. The researcher is using cross

sectional techniques to collect the data from the respondents in one time, and longitudinal to conduct a repetitive data collection (Malhotra, 2012).

Table 2. All Variable Descriptive

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Individual_Needs	150	1	6	5.33	.675
Personal_Preferences	150	1	6	5.37	.577
Tech_Savvy	150	1	6	5.41	.628
Job_Performance	150	1	6	5.26	.661
Working_Environment	150	2	6	5.25	.489
Valid N (listwise)	150				

There are 5 variables in total that will be listed in this study. Those variables are individual needs, personal preferences, working environment, tech-savvy, and job performance. In the individual needs variable, the minimum is 1.00, the maximum is 6.28 and the mean is 5.33 which means the respondents who works for E-Commerce is more concerned for their needs such as salary and comfort. In the personal preferences variable, the minimum is 1.00, the maximum is 6.07, and the mean is 5.37, which means the respondents are more concerned for their personal preferences such as enjoy to do their work. In the working environment variable, the minimum is 2.11, the maximum is 5.96, and the mean is 5.25, which means the respondents are more concerned for their working environment such as trustworthy and harmony environment of work. In tech-savvy variable, the minimum is 1.00, the maximum is 6.02, and the means is 5.41, which means the respondents are more concerned for their tech-savvy lifestyle such as understanding in technology. In job performance variable, the minimum is 1.00, the maximum is 6.05, and the mean is 5.26, which means millennial generation who works for E-Commerce are confident, dedicated, and highly motivated towards their job performance at work.

4.2 Regression analysis

Table 3. E-Commerce Industry Respondents

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	R Square	B	ANOVA	Sig	Conclusion
Job Performance			Constant -.460			
	Individual Needs	.687	.305	.000	.000	H1 Accepted
	Personal Preferences		.238		.047	H2 Accepted
	Working Environment		.296		.006	H3 Accepted
	Tech-Savvy		.233		.001	H4 Accepted

The table 3 above shown that the quality of the data is significant since the total value of ANOVA is lower than 0.5. All of the the variable are have a significant impact since all of their significant level are below 0.5. Individual needs with 0.00, personal preferences with 0.47, working environment with 0.06, and tech-savvy with 0.01. The table also shows the value of r-square, which is 0.687 showing that 68.7% of the data are aligned around the regression line. In conclusion, all of the hypotheses are accepted since all of them are scored below 0.5 of the significant level.

$$Y (\text{Job Performance}) = 0.460 + 0.00*\text{Individual needs} + 0.47*\text{Personal preferences} + 0.06*\text{Working environment} + 0.01*\text{Tech-savvy}$$

4.3 Correlation

The researcher have to find the correlations between the variables. By calculating all of the variables, the researcher using spearman correlation method in order to check if there is a correlation within the variable. The researcher have to determine all of the 5 variables which are individual needs, personal preferences, working environment, tech-savvy, and job performance. The correlation between variables will considered significant if the level of p-value is lower than 0.05 (2-tailed).

Table 4. Spearman Correlation
Correlations

			Individual_Needs	Personal_Preferences	Working_Environment	Tech_Savvy	Job_Performance
Spearman's rho	Individual_Needs	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.584**	.416**	.435**	.574**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	150	150	150	150	150
	Personal_Preferences	Correlation Coefficient	.584**	1.000	.683**	.475**	.602**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	150	150	150	150	150
	Working_Environment	Correlation Coefficient	.416**	.683**	1.000	.334**	.545**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
		N	150	150	150	150	150
	Tech_Savvy	Correlation Coefficient	.435**	.475**	.334**	1.000	.499**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
		N	150	150	150	150	150
	Job_Performance	Correlation Coefficient	.574**	.602**	.545**	.499**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	150	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 4 above represents the value of correlations between variables. There are 5 variables including individual needs, personal preferences, working environment, tech-savvy, and job performance. All of those variables above have correlations with each other, with the total value of significant level 0.00 (2-tailed). The more the closer the value correlation coefficient to 1.00, the better the value of the correlation itself. The highest correlation coefficient value is 0.68 which is working environment to personal preferences and the lowest correlation coefficient value is 0.33 which is techsavvy with working environment. However, they are all still have positive correlation among all of the variables.

4.4 Summary

Table 5. The Summary of Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Text	Findings
H1	Individual needs is positively related to Job Performance	Supported
H2	Personal preferences is positively related to Job Performance	Supported
H3	Work environment is positively related to Job Performance	Supported
H4	Tech-savvy is positively related to Job Performance	Supported

The table 5 above is represents the summary of all of the 4 hypothesis testing that have been mentioned in the previous chapter. From the table above it is shown that each independent variable that are individual needs, personal preference, working environment, and tech-savvy are supported towards the dependent variable which is job performance. All of those variables are positively related towards job performance.

5 Conclusion

E-Commerce is one of the most popular industries to work for millennial generation based on this research. Those 5 factors are influencing their job performances. Individual needs are important for millennial that is working for e-commerce, based on the answer of the respondents. There are things that could be improve in e-commerce industry to make the millennial generation more comfortable, paid their salary on time, and appreciation towards their work is needed to improve their motivation. Personal preferences are also important since most of the respondents need to enjoy their work in order to perform better in their tasks given, job promotion will also motivate the worker to improve their job performance, they encourage to work harder in order to get higher salary, happiness of their accomplishment, and they have to feel comfortable of their job. Working environment also important because they proper training to motivate their work, gain trust and respect with their coworker will increase their motivation, maintain good relationship and harmony with subordinate will improve their motivation, and comfortable and safety environment will satisfy the employees. Lastly, tech-savvy is the other important factor that influencing millennial since they need understanding on technology to help them do their daily task, It is also important for employees to keep up with technology growth, technology become very handy on daily task, and they can finish faster and better with the help of technology. All of those factors or variables need to be improve by E-Commerce industry in order to increase the motivation of their employees that will affect their job performances to perform better in their work.

References

- [1] Canarelli, M. (2017, February 22). The Perks of Hiring Millennials. Retrieved October 20, 2017, from <https://www.business.com/articles/going-millennialthe-perks-of-hiring-generation-y/>.
- [2] Gangesshwer, D. K. (2016). [Http://journal.ru/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/d2016-154.pdf](http://journal.ru/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/d2016-154.pdf). E-Commerce or Internet Marketing: A Business Review from Indian Context,1-2. doi:10.18411/d-2016-154
- [3] Kane, S. (2017, October 23). What Employers Should Know About Their Gen Y Employees. Retrieved October 24, 2017, from <https://www.thebalance.com/common-characteristics-of-generation-yprofessionals-2164683>
- [4] Lücking, R. (2014). Die Flechten Deutschlands Wirth, V. M. Hauck, and M. Schulz. 2013. Die Flechten Deutschlands, Band 1 and 2 (in German). 1244 pp., with 46 figures and 845 color photographs. Eugen Ulmer, Stuttgart. [ISBN 978-3-8001-5903-1 (Print); 978-3-8001-8909-0 (electronic PDF)]. Price €159.00 shipping and postage (print, hardcover); €139.99

- Euro (electronic PDF). Available from <http://www.ulmer.de>. The Bryologist, 117(2), 219-221. doi:10.1639/bryologist-d-14-00020.1
- [5] Motherudin, F. (2015). [Http://www.jssoftware.us/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=150&id=2309](http://www.jssoftware.us/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=150&id=2309). Pengaruh Workplace Fun Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Berdasarkan Generation Differences, 10(3), 374-383. doi:10.17706/jsw.10.3.374-383
- [6] Prasatya, A. (2017, April 30). Markas Besar E-Commerce Indonesia. Retrieved October 15, 2017, from <https://iprice.co.id/trend/insights/markasbesar-e-commerce-indonesia/>
- [7] A. P. (2017, January 25). What to Expect From Indonesian E-Commerce 2017. Retrieved October 15, 2017, from <https://www.techinasia.com/talk/5-trends-indonesian-ecommerce-2017>
- [8] Leblebici, D. (2012). Impact of workplace quality on employee's productivity: Case study of a bank in Turkey. *Journal of Business, Economics and Finance*, 1, 38-49
- [9] Naharuddin, N. M., & Sadegi, M. (2013). Factors of workplace environment that affect employees performance: A case study of Miyazu Malaysia. *International Journal of Independent Research and Studies*, 2, 66-78.
- [10] Oladipo, S. E. (2009). Psychological empowerment and development. *Edo Journal of Counselling*, 2, 118-126.
- [11] Ollukkaran, B. A., & Gunaseelan, R. (2012). A study on the impact of work environment on employee performance. *Namex International Journal of Management Research*, 2, 70-85
- [12] Oluseyi, S., & Ayo, H. T. (2009). Influence of work motivation, leadership effectiveness and time management of employees' performance in some selected industries in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 16, 1450-2887.
- [13] Renner, P. (2004). Workers physical surrounding. Impact bottom line accounting: Smarts Pros.com
- [14] Smerek, R.E & Peterson, M. (2007) EXAMINING HERZBERG'S THEORY: Improving Job Satisfaction among Non-Academic Employees at a University. *Research in Higher Education*, Vol. 48 No.2.
- [15] Sinha, E. S. (2001). The skills and career path of an effective project manager *International Journal of Project Management*, 19, 1-7
- [16] Stup, R. (2003). Control the factors that influence employee success: Managing the Hispanic workforce Conference. Cornell University and Pennsylvania State University
- [17] Subramani, S. P. V. (2011). A study on link between workplace environment and employee performance at big bazaar, Chennai. (Master dissertation, Sona College of Technology, 2011).